

Fra proteins influencing filament integrity, diazotrophy and localization of septal protein SepJ in the heterocyst-forming cyanobacterium *Anabaena* sp.

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Summary

Anabaena sp. strain PCC 7120 is a filamentous cyanobacterium that can fix N₂ in differentiated cells called heterocysts, which exchange nutritional and regulatory compounds with the neighboring photosynthetic vegetative cells. The cells in the filament appear to be joined by some protein structures, of which SepJ (FraG) that is located at the cell poles in the intercellular septa and is needed for filament integrity seems to be a component. Other known proteins required for filament integrity include FraC and FraH. Whereas *fraC* (*alr2392*) was constitutively expressed as an operon together with two downstream genes, *alr2393* (*fraD*) and *alr2394* (*fraE*), *fraH* (*alr1603*) was induced under nitrogen deprivation. Mutants of each of the four *fra* genes showed filament fragmentation under nitrogen deprivation and did not grow diazotrophically, although they formed heterocysts. The *fraC* and *fraD* mutants showed an impaired localization of SepJ at the intercellular septa and were hampered in the intercellular transfer of the fluorescent probe calcein. As shown with GFP fusions, FraC and FraD are also located at the intercellular septa. Therefore, at least three different proteins, SepJ, FraC and FraD, influence the architecture and function of the intercellular septa in the *Anabaena* filaments.

Introduction

The heterocyst-forming cyanobacteria grow as filaments or trichomes. When deprived of combined nitrogen, some vegetative cells in the filament differentiate into heterocysts that are specialized in the fixation of atmospheric nitrogen gas (Wolk *et al.*, 1994). Heterocyst differentiation requires NtcA, the global N-control transcription factor of cyanobacteria, and HetR, a regulator needed specifically for differentiation (Herrero *et al.*, 2004; Xu *et al.*, 2008). In the course of differentiation, a heterocyst-specific cell envelope is deposited consisting of an external polysaccharide layer and an internal layer of glycolipids that are needed for protection of nitrogenase against oxygen (Wolk *et al.*, 1994). The mature heterocysts express genes related to the diazotrophic metabolism including the *nifHDK* operon encoding nitrogenase (Elhai and Wolk, 1990). In contrast to the vegetative cells, heterocysts do not perform oxygenic photosynthesis and concomitant CO₂ fixation. As a consequence of this specialization in cellular function, in a diazotrophic filament carbon moves from the vegetative cells to heterocysts and fixed nitrogen moves from heterocysts to the vegetative cells (Wolk *et al.*, 1994). The growth of the filament strictly depends on this exchange of materials, and regulatory compounds such as some inhibitors of differentiation produced by heterocysts (Wolk, 1967), of which PatS or a PatS-related signal is a known example (Yoon and Golden, 1998), are also intercellularly transferred.

A cyanobacterial filament consists of a string of individual cells, and no plasmodesmata-like structures appear to be present (Flores *et al.*, 2006; Mariscal *et al.*, 2007). The cyanobacteria bear a Gram-negative type of cell envelope, and the outer membrane is continuous along the filament (Flores *et al.*, 2006), which could help to keep the cells together in the filament. Specific proteins appear also to join cells or stabilize cell junctions, since mutants exhibiting filament fragmentation have been identified among mutants unable to grow diazotrophically isolated from *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 (Buikema and Haselkorn,

1991b; Ernst *et al.*, 1992). Three *fra* genes have been identified (Bauer *et al.*, 1995; Nayar *et al.*, 2007), which lie in different locations on the chromosome and correspond to open reading frames *alr1603* (*fraH*), *alr2392* (*fraC*), and *alr2338* (*fraG*) of the *Anabaena* genomic sequence (Kaneko *et al.*, 2001). The latter gene has been independently identified by us and termed *sepJ* because it was found to encode a protein that is conspicuously located at the cell poles in the intercellular septa (Flores *et al.*, 2007). The SepJ protein sequence shows an N-terminal extracytoplasmic domain that carries coiled-coil motifs, which might be involved in protein-protein interactions, and a C-terminal domain that is homologous to permeases in the drug/metabolite exporter (DME) family (Flores *et al.*, 2007).

We have recently observed diffusion of calcein, a 622-Da hydrophilic fluorescent tracer that can be loaded into the cytoplasm, from cell to cell in filaments of *Anabaena* spp. (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008). Intercellular exchange of calcein is impaired in a *sepJ* mutant, suggesting the involvement of SepJ in a channel that connects neighboring cells and allows the transfer of calcein. To ask whether other proteins could contribute to such a channel, which would be important for multicellularity, we further investigated the *fra* genes. We found that *fraC* is part of an operon including two other *fra* genes, and we addressed the role of the identified Fra proteins in heterocyst differentiation, in the localization of SepJ at the cell poles and in the intercellular transfer of calcein.

Results

Expression of the fra genes

The *fraC* (*alr2392*) gene (Bauer *et al.*, 1995) is part of a cluster of genes that also contains *alr2393* (here denoted *fraD*) and *alr2394* (*fraE*) (Kaneko *et al.*, 2001). To test whether these genes constitute an operon, RT-PCR analysis was performed with RNA isolated from *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 grown with ammonium, nitrate or N₂ as the nitrogen source.

After retrotranscription with oligonucleotide primers from *fraD* and *fraE*, amplification products were obtained with primer pairs from *fraC* and *fraD* and from *fraD* and *fraE*, respectively, thus showing co-transcription of the three genes under the three tested N regimes (see Suppl. Fig S1).

To analyze the level of expression of the operon, Northern blot analysis was performed with RNA isolated from cultures of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 grown with ammonium and incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen for several periods of time up to 24 h (Fig. 1A). Double-stranded gene probes of *fraC* and *fraD* hybridized to RNA molecules of different sizes up to about 3.1 kb. A double-stranded *fraE* probe hybridized strongly to RNA molecules of about 1.35 kb in size (not shown). Using *fraE* single-stranded probes, this transcript was found to correspond to an antisense RNA that will be characterized elsewhere. The *fraE* probe complementary to the operon transcript, however, hybridized with mRNA molecules of sizes similar to those detected with *fraC* and *fraD* probes (Fig. 1A). RNA molecules of 3.1 to 3.3 kb could correspond to transcripts covering the whole operon, which is predicted to be at least 2,419 bp long. No clear induction was observed during the N step-down time-course for the *fra* operon transcript (Fig. 1A), and Northern analysis carried out with RNA isolated from ammonium-grown filaments of *Anabaena ntcA* (Frías *et al.*, 1994) and *hetR* (Buikema and Haselkorn, 1991a) mutants subjected to N deprivation for several periods of time up to 24 h indicated that expression of the operon was not affected by any of these mutations (Fig. 1A). It should be noted that, consistent with Bauer *et al.* (1995) who failed to detect the *fraC* transcript, the *fraC* operon transcript was difficult to detect requiring a long exposure in the Northern analysis, which indicates a low expression level.

The *fraH* gene (*alr1603*) is part of a cluster of genes that also includes *alr1602*, *alr1604* and *alr1605* (*alr1603* to *alr1604* depicted in Fig. 1B). In N-deprivation experiments, a *fraH* probe hybridized with RNA molecules of about 1.1 and 2 kb, respectively, that were

readily detected (Fig. 1B). The 1.1-kb transcript could cover *fraH*, which is 870-bp long, and the 2-kb transcript could cover either *alr1602-fraH* or *fraH-alr1604* (each of about 1.76 kb). Whereas a Northern blot analysis with an *alr1602* probe showed bands of 0.96 and 2 kb, respectively (Fig. 1B), Northern blot analysis with an *alr1604* probe showed a different pattern and weaker hybridization (not shown). We conclude that *alr1602* and *fraH* can be co-transcribed as a 2-kb mRNA but also produce independent transcripts. ORF *alr1602* encodes 6-phosphogluconolactonase, and its mutation results in a Fox⁻ phenotype (Bauer, 1994, cited by Xu *et al.*, 2008). Expression of *alr1602-fraH* and *fraH* took place at appreciable levels in ammonium-grown cells and was further induced during the first 9 h of nitrogen deprivation (Fig. 1B). In the *ntcA* and *hetR* mutants, expression was impaired under nitrogen deprivation but not in the ammonium-grown cells (Fig. 1B).

Generation and phenotype of fra mutants

Inactivation of *fraC* and *fraH* has been previously shown to produce a filament fragmentation phenotype (Bauer *et al.*, 1995). To test a possible related role of the other genes in the *fra* operon, *fraD* and *fraE* were inactivated, and *fraC* and *fraH* were also mutated for comparison and further characterization of the mutants. To avoid possible polar effects of the mutations, *fraC*, *fraD* and *fraH* were inactivated by introducing in-frame deletions that were prepared by removing an internal fragment of each of these genes, whereas *fraE*, which is the last gene in the *fra* operon, was inactivated by insertion of a plasmid (Fig. 2A; see Experimental procedures for details). Strains carrying deletions in *fraC*, *fraD* and *fraH* were named CSVT1, CSVT2 and CSVT4, respectively, and a strain carrying an insertion in *fraE* was named CSVT3. All these strains were homozygous for the mutant chromosomes (Fig. 2B).

The four *fra* mutants grew normally in media supplemented with a source of combined N, either nitrate or ammonium, but did not grow fixing N₂ (see growth on solid medium in

Fig. 2C). In shaken liquid cultures, the filaments of the mutants fragmented extensively upon incubation in combined N-free media, and filament fragmentation was already evident 24 h after N step-down (Fig. 3). These results indicated that the two newly characterized genes, *alr2393* (*fraD*) and *alr2394* (*fraE*), are, like *fraC* and *fraH*, required for filament integrity. However, for the *fraC* mutant in the presence of combined nitrogen, Bauer *et al.* (1995) observed a short-filament phenotype that was not evident with our *fraC* mutant.

When the mutants were incubated in combined N-free medium, many short filaments were observed that contained heterocysts, mainly at terminal positions (Fig. 4). Strains CSVT1 through CSVT4 produced the heterocyst polysaccharide layer as shown by staining with Alcian blue (Fig. 4), although staining of heterocysts was somewhat irregular (in the sense that some heterocysts were not stained) in strains CSVT3 and CSVT4. The four mutants also produced heterocyst-specific glycolipids, although in strain CSVT3 synthesis was delayed with respect to the wild type and the other mutants (Suppl. Fig. S2). The *nifHDK* operon was induced in response to nitrogen deprivation, as expected, producing transcripts corresponding to *nifH*, *nifHD* and *nifHDK* (Suppl. Fig. S3), but whereas transcript levels in mutants CSVT1, CSVT2 and CSVT4 were similar to those in the wild type, they were relatively low in strain CSVT3. Regarding nitrogenase, strains CSVT1 and CSVT2 developed activity slowly, attaining appreciable nitrogenase levels that could be determined under both oxic and anoxic conditions after 48 h of incubation in combined N-free medium (Table 1). In contrast, strains CSVT3 and CSVT4 showed undetectable or negligible nitrogenase activity when determined under oxic conditions and very low activity when determined under anoxic conditions after being incubated in combined N-free medium for 48 h. Thus, heterocyst differentiation was observed in the four *fra* mutants, which produced appreciable levels of *nifHDK* transcript under oxic conditions, but only the *fraC* and *fraD* mutants exhibited appreciable levels of nitrogenase activity.

Relation to SepJ

Anabaena sp. strain CSAM137 carries a translational fusion of GFP to the carboxy-terminal part of SepJ (Flores *et al.*, 2007). This strain can grow diazotrophically indicating that the SepJ-GFP fusion protein, which localizes to the cell poles at the intercellular septa in the filament, retains SepJ function. The *sepJ-gfp* construct was transferred to the *fra* mutants producing strains which carried the SepJ-GFP translational fusion in each of the *fra* backgrounds: strain CSVT9, $\Delta fraC$ *sepJ-gfp*; strain CSVT10, $\Delta fraD$ *sepJ-gfp*; strain CSVT11, *fraE::pCSV3 sepJ-gfp*; and strain CSVT12, $\Delta fraH$ *sepJ-gfp*. Localization of SepJ-GFP was studied by confocal microscopy in filaments of these strains cultivated in ammonium- or nitrate-containing medium and in filaments incubated in the absence of combined N for 8 and 26 h; strain CSAM137 was used as a control. In the *fraC* and *fraD* mutants, localization of SepJ-GFP was altered showing a less focused positioning at the intercellular septa than that observed in strain CSAM137 (Fig. 5). Interestingly, focusing enhanced after N step-down, especially in the *fraC* mutant, in which numerous constricted septa with focalized SepJ-GFP were observed after 26 h without combined nitrogen (Fig. 5). In contrast, localization of SepJ-GFP at the cell poles in the *fraE* and *fraH* mutants was similar to that observed in strain CSAM137. As in the wild-type background, in the four *fra* mutants SepJ-GFP localized to a mid-cell ring when cell division starts (Fig. 5 and not shown).

A *sepJ* insertional mutant is impaired in the intercellular transfer of calcein that can be observed after photobleaching of this fluorescent probe in a cell of the wild-type filament (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008). An exchange coefficient that quantitatively describes this intercellular transfer of calcein can be derived from fluorescence recovery after photobleaching (FRAP) experiments (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008). Calcein exchange between vegetative cells was investigated in the *fra* mutants after growth in nitrate-supplemented

cultures and after incubation for 16 h in combined N-free medium; the wild-type strain PCC 7120 was used as a control. The exchange coefficients obtained for the wild type in these experiments were similar to those obtained in our previous work (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008), being somewhat higher in the filaments incubated in combined N-free media than in the presence of nitrate (Table 2). For both nitrate-grown filaments and filaments incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen, calcein transfer was significantly hampered in the *fraC* and *fraD* mutants. In contrast, although also impaired to some extent, calcein transfer took place at appreciable levels in the *fraE* and *fraH* mutants (see Fig. 6 and Table 2). Thus, the FraC and FraD proteins appear to be required for focal localization of SepJ-GFP at the intercellular septa and for intercellular transfer of calcein.

Subcellular localization of FraC and FraD

To address the subcellular localization of FraC and FraD, translational fusions to GFP were prepared. Because the GFP folds efficiently only in the cytoplasm (Drew *et al.*, 2002), the fusions were designed such that the GFP was fused to a predicted cytoplasmic domain in each Fra protein. For FraC, a fusion of the *gfp-mut2* gene to the 3' end of the *fraC* gene (with its termination codon removed) was cloned in vector pCSV3 and transferred to strain PCC 7120 as described in Experimental procedures. A clone that had introduced this construct by single recombination into the *fraC* genomic region was named strain CSVT13, which carries both the *fraC-gfp* fusion gene and a wild-type copy of the *fraC* gene. For FraD, a *gfp-mut2* gene lacking its termination codon was introduced between amino acid residues 1 and 2 of the *fraD* gene, and this construct was transferred to strain PCC 7120 (see Experimental procedures for details). A clone in which the *gfp-fraD* fusion gene had replaced the wild-type *fraD* gene was selected and named strain CSVT21. Both strains, CSVT13 and CSVT21, could grow using ammonium, nitrate or N₂ as the nitrogen source. This was expected for CSVT13, which

keeps an intact copy of *fraC*; however, for strain CSVT21 this observation indicates that the GFP-FraD fusion protein retains FraD function.

Cultures of strains CSVT13 and CSVT21 grown with nitrate or incubated 24 h in the absence of combined nitrogen were analyzed by confocal microscopy (Fig. 7). Both FraC-GFP and GFP-FraD were mainly located at the intercellular septa in the filaments (Fig. 7), but localization at the center of the septum similar to that of SepJ-GFP was not observed, especially for FraC-GFP. Indeed, the localization at the septa was more clear-cut for GFP-FraD than for FraC-GFP, which tended to appear also in the periphery of the cells away from the septa, especially in the filaments that had been incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen. Heterocysts from both strains showed accumulation of the GFP fusions at their edges close to the adjacent vegetative cells. Finally, as is the case for SepJ-GFP, FraC-GFP was also observed in the periphery, midway between the ends of the cells in cells that are starting division (Fig. 7).

As a control GFP fusion to a different cytoplasmic membrane protein, the GFP was fused to Amt1, which is an ammonium/methylammonium transporter (Paz-Yepes *et al.*, 2008) that is expected to reside throughout the cell's cytoplasmic membrane. The *gfp-mut2* gene was fused to the 3' end of *amt1* (lacking the termination codon) and transferred to *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 to produce strain CSVT15 that expresses a translational GFP fusion to the C-terminus of Amt1 (see Experimental procedures for details). Strain CSVT15 was checked by confocal microscopy, and the GFP fluorescence was observed throughout the periphery of the cells both in nitrate-grown filaments and in filaments incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen for 30 h (Fig. 7). These results confirm the specificity of the localization of FraC-GFP and GFP-FraD at the intercellular septa.

Discussion

In *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120, the *fraC* gene, which was originally identified by Bauer *et al.* (1995), forms an operon with two downstream genes, *fraD* and *fraE*. This operon is expressed at relatively low levels both in the presence and absence of combined nitrogen. In contrast, *fraH*, also identified by Bauer *et al.* (1995), is induced under nitrogen deprivation, and expression under these conditions is dependent on NtcA and HetR pointing to a function in the heterocysts or in heterocyst-containing filaments. Inactivation of the four genes, *fraC*, *fraD*, *fraE* and *fraH*, produces a filament fragmentation phenotype that is manifest under nitrogen deprivation, and the corresponding mutant strains are unable to grow diazotrophically. Nonetheless, in these mutants, heterocysts differentiate upon nitrogen deprivation. These heterocysts contain heterocyst-specific polysaccharides and glycolipids and express the *nifHDK* operon. However, nitrogenase activity was detected at significant levels in strains CSVT1 (Δ *fraC*) and CSVT2 (Δ *fraD*) but not in strains CSVT3 (*fraE*::pCSV3) and CSVT4 (Δ *fraH*) indicating a role of FraE and FraH in the conformation of a functional heterocyst or in the development of nitrogenase activity. The basis for this role of FraE and FraH is unknown. In contrast to the *fra* mutants, in the *sepJ* mutants heterocyst differentiation is blocked between the stages of formation of the envelope polysaccharide layer and production of heterocyst glycolipids (Flores *et al.*, 2007). Therefore, whereas the Fra proteins appear to be needed for the functional operation of heterocyst-containing filaments, SepJ is required for the development of such filaments.

Although expression of the *sepJ* gene is increased in response to nitrogen deprivation and the *sepJ* mutants show filament fragmentation most extensively under these conditions, these mutants also show fragmentation in media containing combined nitrogen indicating that SepJ is essential for filament integrity independent of the nitrogen source (Flores *et al.*, 2007; Nayar *et al.*, 2007). In contrast, the *fra* mutants fragment only, as compared to the wild type,

upon nitrogen deprivation (Fig. 3). Whereas the observed induction of *fraH* under nitrogen deprivation is consistent with a role of FraH in filament integrity especially under diazotrophic conditions, the *fraC* operon is expressed at similar levels in the presence and the absence of combined nitrogen. It is possible that the *Anabaena* filaments are more fragile in the absence of combined nitrogen, the need for proteins involved in keeping the cells together in the filament becoming most stringent under these conditions.

SepJ-GFP localizes to a ring similar to a Z-ring when cell division starts, and gets focalized at the cell poles upon constriction of the cell division septum (Flores *et al.*, 2007). In the *fraC* and *fraD* mutants, initial localization of SepJ-GFP to a cell division ring is not affected, but SepJ-GFP localization at the cell poles in the intercellular septa is impaired. Therefore, FraC and FraD could be needed to shape the mature SepJ-containing septum or for keeping SepJ at this location. The subcellular localization of FraC and FraD was probed by the use of GFP fusions. A GFP-FraD fusion localizes at the intercellular septa similar to, but not as focused as, SepJ-GFP. In contrast, FraC-GFP localizes to a ring, similar to a Z ring, when cell division starts and mainly to the intercellular septa when cell division is completed, but localization is looser than that observed with SepJ-GFP or GFP-FraD (Fig. 7). FraD is a predicted integral cytoplasmic membrane protein that carries a 167-residue long C-terminal extracytoplasmic segment containing two strongly predicted coiled-coil motifs, and FraC is also a predicted integral cytoplasmic membrane protein. The architecture of the intercellular septa in the *Anabaena* filament, which contains at least three cytoplasmic membrane-bound proteins, SepJ, FraC and FraD, represents an important novel topic for future research.

Inactivation of *fraC* and *fraD* also hampers intercellular transfer of calcein. We have previously observed that a *sepJ* mutant is impaired in calcein transfer (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008) but, because inactivation of *sepJ* leads to extensive filament fragmentation, the possibility remained that the effect of the *sepJ* mutation on calcein transfer was indirect. The

fact that mutation of two independent genes, *fraC* and *fraD*, results in both impaired SepJ-GFP localization and hampered calcein transfer, even in nitrate-containing medium, corroborates a possible dependence of calcein transfer on SepJ, which can be an element of a cell-to-cell joining protein complex with channel function. FraC and FraD are needed for the calcein transfer pathway to be operative but not for differentiation of heterocysts expressing nitrogenase activity. Therefore, the channel that allows the passage of calcein is not needed for heterocyst differentiation but could be required for the intercellular exchange of C and N compounds that supports diazotrophic growth. On the other hand, because heterocyst differentiation takes place in the *fraC* and *fraD* mutants, exchange of regulatory compounds influencing heterocyst differentiation should involve other pathways for intercellular molecular exchange, which could include the continuous periplasm of these organisms (Flores *et al.*, 2006; Mariscal *et al.*, 2007).

Experimental procedures

Bacterial strains and growth conditions

Anabaena sp. (also known as *Nostoc* sp.) strain PCC 7120 was grown in BG11 (containing NaNO₃), BG11₀ (free of combined nitrogen) or BG11₀ + ammonium (BG11₀ containing 4 mM NH₄Cl and, respectively, 8 mM TES-NaOH buffer, pH 7.5) medium at 30 °C in the light (75 μE m⁻² s⁻¹), in shaken (80-90 r.p.m.) liquid cultures or in medium solidified with 1 % Difco agar. Alternatively, cultures (referred to as bubbled cultures) were supplemented with 10 mM of NaHCO₃ and bubbled with a mixture of CO₂ and air (1 % v/v). In this case, the ammonium-containing medium was supplemented with 6 mM NH₄Cl and 12 mM TES-NaOH buffer (pH 7.5). The *hetR* mutant, *Anabaena* sp. strain 216 (Buikema and Haselkorn, 1991a), was grown in BG11 medium, and the *ntcA* mutant, strain CSE2 (Frías *et al.*, 1994), was grown in BG11₀ + ammonium medium supplemented with Sm and Sp. Antibiotics were used

at the following concentrations: Sm, 2-5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$; Sp, 2-5 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ and Nm, 10-50 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. DNA was isolated from *Anabaena* sp. by the method of Cai and Wolk (1990).

Escherichia coli DH5 α was used for plasmid constructions. It and strains HB101 and ED8654, used for conjugations with *Anabaena* sp., were grown in LB medium, supplemented when appropriate with antibiotics at standard concentrations (Ausubel *et al.*, 2008).

Construction of mutants

To inactivate *alr2392*, *alr2393* and *alr1603*, DNA fragments upstream and downstream from the central region of each gene were amplified by standard PCR using as template DNA from *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and oligonucleotide primers all2391-1/fraC-2 and fraC-3/R1 for *alr2392*, F1/alr2393-2 and alr2393-3/R2 for *alr2393*, and F9/alr1603-2 and alr1603-1/R9 for *alr1603* (all deoxyoligonucleotide primers are listed in Suppl. Table S1). The upstream and downstream DNA fragments from each gene were cloned in pMBL-T (Dominion MBL, Spain), sequenced and inserted together, in direct orientation, into pCSRO. This plasmid is derived from pRL500 (Elhai and Wolk, 1988a), which can be mobilized by conjugation, and carries the *sacB* gene for positive selection and an Sm^R/Sp^R determinant (cassette C.S3, Elhai and Wolk, 1988a) instead of the original Ap^R determinant. The produced plasmids, pCSV6, pCSV2 and pCSV8, bear cloned *Anabaena* DNA from the *alr2392*, *alr2393* and *alr1603* loci with internal gene in-frame deletions of 366 bp, 783 bp and 645 bp, respectively.

For inactivation of *alr2394*, an internal fragment of 408 bp was amplified by PCR using primers F8 and R5, which included BamHI sites in their 5' ends, and genomic DNA from strain PCC 7120. The amplified fragment was cloned into vector pMBL-T and transferred as a BamHI-ended fragment to BamHI-digested pCSV3 (which is pRL500 in which the Ap^R gene has been substituted by an Sm^R/Sp^R gene cassette [Elhai and Wolk,

1988a)] producing pCSV4. For simplicity, we refer by its plasmid name to the portion of pCSV3 inserted in *alr2394*.

Conjugation of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 with *E. coli* HB101 carrying the cargo plasmid (pCSV2, pCSV4, pCSV6 or pCSV8) with helper and methylation plasmid pRL623 was effected by the conjugative plasmid pRL443, carried in *E. coli* ED8654, and performed as described (Elhai and Wolk, 1988b) with selection for resistance to Sm/Sp. For conjugations involving pCSV2, pCSV6 or pCSV8, filaments of twelve to twenty four Sm^R/Sp^R clones were spread on BG11 medium supplemented with 5% sucrose (Cai and Wolk, 1990), and individual Suc^R colonies were checked by PCR looking for clones that had substituted the wild-type locus by a deleted locus. Such clones with deleted loci appeared with a frequency of about 25% to 40% depending on the tested construct. The genetic structure of selected clones was studied by PCR with DNA from those clones and primers F6/R1 for *alr2392*, F1/R2 for *alr2393*, F7/R8 and F8/R8 for *alr2394*, and F9/R9 for *alr1603*. Clones homozygous for the mutant chromosomes were named strain CSVT1 ($\Delta alr2392$), CSVT2 ($\Delta alr2393$), CSVT3 (*alr2394::pCSV3*) and CSVT4 ($\Delta alr1604$).

GFP fusions

Plasmid pCSAM137 carrying a *sepJ-gfp* fusion and an Sm^R/Sp^R determinant (Flores *et al.*, 2007) was transferred to strains CSVT1, CSVT2 and CSVT4 as previously described for *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 (Flores *et al.*, 2007). For conjugation into strain CSVT3 (*alr2394::pCSV3*), which is itself resistant to Sm/Sp, plasmid pCSV22 was constructed by transferring the *sepJ-gfp* fusion from pCSAM135 (Flores *et al.*, 2007) to pRL424 (Nm^R; Elhai and Wolk, 1988a) digesting both plasmids with HindIII. Conjugation was effected as described above, but with selection for Nm^R.

For construction of a FraC-GFP fusion, an 835-bp DNA fragment was amplified, using *Anabaena* DNA as template and primers all2391-3 and fraC-6, and cloned in pMBL-T producing pCSV13. An ApaI-EcoRV fragment from pCSAM135 carrying the *gfp-mut2* gene (Flores *et al.*, 2007) was inserted into pCSV13 digested with the same enzymes, producing pCSV35, and a PstI DNA fragment from this plasmid carrying the *fraC-gfp* fusion was inserted into mobilizable vector pCSV3 ($\text{Sm}^{\text{R}}/\text{Sp}^{\text{R}}$) producing pCSV36. This plasmid was transferred to *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 by conjugation as described above. $\text{Sm}^{\text{R}}/\text{Sp}^{\text{R}}$ clones were selected for, and their genomic structure in the *fraC* region was tested by PCR with primers F6 (which lies outside of the construct) and gfp-4 to test recombination in the correct place, and with primers F6 and alr2393-10 (both lying outside of the construct) to test for segregation of the pCSV36-carrying chromosomes.

For construction of a GFP-FraD fusion, two DNA fragments were cloned into pGEM-T after amplification by PCR using *Anabaena* DNA as template: (i) a 785-bp fragment carrying *fraC* and upstream sequences amplified using primers fraC-11 and fraC-18, and (ii) a 1,048-bp fragment carrying *fraD* and a short downstream sequence amplified using primers alr2393-21 and alr2393-24. Using pCE18 (E. Olmedo-Verd, unpublished) as template, a *gfp-mut2* gene lacking its termination codon was amplified with primers gfp-6 and gfp-HindIII. The *fraC* and *fraD* fragments were cloned together in pIC20R with the *gfp-mut2* gene, inserted downstream of the *fraD* GTG start codon, and the whole *fraC-gfp-fraD* fragment, in which *gfp-fraD* is a single fusion gene, was removed with SmaI and EcoRV and inserted into BamHI-digested, Klenow-filled mobilizable vector pCSR0 ($\text{Sm}^{\text{R}}/\text{Sp}^{\text{R}}$, *sacB*), producing pCSV56. This plasmid was transferred to *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 by conjugation as described above. $\text{Sm}^{\text{R}}/\text{Sp}^{\text{R}}$ clones were selected for that should have incorporated into their genome the whole pCSV56 by a single recombination event. Then, clones resistant to 5% sucrose were isolated and tested for sensitivity to Sm/Sp. Sucrose^R $\text{Sm}^{\text{S}}/\text{Sp}^{\text{S}}$ clones should

have lost the vector portion of pCSV56 through a second recombination event. Clones in which the *fraD* gene has been replaced by the *gfp-fraD* fusion gene were identified by PCR with primers all2391-3 and *gfp-4* and corroborated with primers *gfp-6* and R2. Segregation of the mutant chromosomes was tested by PCR with primers all2391-3 and R2 (both lying outside of the construct).

For construction of Amt1-GFP, a 789-bp fragment from the 3' region of *amt1* (*alr0991*) was amplified by PCR using genomic DNA from strain PCC 7120 and primers 7120-*amt1-8* and 7120-*amt1-9* that included *Cla*I and *Eco*RV sites, respectively, in their 5' ends. The amplified fragment was cloned into vector pMBL-T producing pCSV28 and transferred as a *Sac*I-*Eco*RV fragment to pCSAM135 (Flores *et al.*, 2007) digested with same enzymes producing pCSV41, in which the *gfp-mut2* gene is fused to the last amino acid-encoding codon of *amt1*. The *amt1-gfp-mut2* fusion was checked by sequencing and transferred as a *Kpn*I fragment to pCSV3 producing plasmid pCSV42. This plasmid was transferred to *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 by conjugation as described above. *Sm*^R/*Sp*^R clones that should have incorporated pCSV42 by single recombination were selected for and their genetic structure was checked by PCR with primers 7120-*amt1-11*, 7120-*amt1-18* and *gfp-4*.

RT-PCR and Northern blot analysis

Isolation of total RNA from *Anabaena* sp. was done as described previously for Gram-negative bacteria (Ausubel *et al.*, 2008). For RT-PCR experiments, 10 µg of strain PCC 7120 total RNA was mixed with 40 pmol of oligonucleotide R1 or R2 in the presence of 10 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.0, 150 mM KCl and 1 mM EDTA, heated for 10 min at 85 °C and then at 50 °C for 1 h for annealing. The extension reactions were carried out at 47 °C for 1 h in a final volume of 45 µl containing the whole annealing reaction, 0.25 mM each deoxynucleoside

triphosphate, 200 U of reverse transcriptase (Superscript II; Invitrogen) and the buffer recommended by the transcriptase provider. To control for the presence of contaminating DNA, samples containing 10 µg of RNA, 40 pmol of oligonucleotides and 1 µg of RNase A (DNase free; Roche) were incubated in a 45 µl reaction volume at 37 °C for 15 min. PCR was carried out with 2–5 µl of retrotranscription mixture or RNase-treated sample as the template and oligonucleotides F1 or F2 and R1 or R2 as primers. Samples containing the same oligonucleotides and strain PCC 7120 genomic DNA as the template were run in parallel and used as control. PCR was performed by standard procedures, and the PCR products were resolved by electrophoresis in a 0.7% agarose gel.

For Northern blots, 15 µg of RNA were loaded per lane and electrophoresed in denaturing 1% agarose formaldehyde gels. Hybridizations were performed as previously described (Paz-Yepes *et al.*, 2007). DNA probes were generated by PCR using *Anabaena* DNA and the oligonucleotide primers indicated in each case. As control of RNA loading and transfer efficiency, the filters were hybridized with a probe of the RNase P RNA gene (*rnpB*) from strain PCC 7120 (Vioque, 1997). Probes were labeled with a DNA labeling kit (Ready to Go, Amersham Pharmacia Biotech) and [α -³²P]dCTP. Radioactive areas in Northern blot hybridizations were visualized and quantified with a Cyclone storage phosphor system (Packard).

Growth tests, glycolipid analysis and nitrogenase activity

Protein concentration was determined by a modified Lowry procedure (Markwell *et al.*, 1978). Chlorophyll *a* (Chl) content of cultures was determined by the method of Mackinney (1941).

For glycolipid analysis, filaments of *Anabaena* sp. grown in BG11 medium (in the presence of Sm and Sp for the CSVT3 mutant) were harvested, washed with nitrogen-free

medium and incubated in BG11₀ medium bubbled with air/CO₂ for 24 or 48 h. Cultures were then harvested and washed with buffer 1 containing 50 mM imidazol and 0.5 mM EDTA (pH 8.0), and the filaments were broken by passage through a French press at 3,000 p.s.i. Samples were enriched in heterocysts after successive steps of centrifugation (200 g, 10 min, room temperature) and washing with buffer 1. Purity of heterocyst preparations was examined by microscopy. Whole filaments or isolated heterocysts from two independent cultures of each strain were analyzed. Lipids were extracted with chloroform-methanol (2:1 v/v), concentrated under N₂, and chromatographed on thin layers of silica gel (Nichols *et al.*, 1968). Heterocyst glycolipids were identified as described (Winkenbach *et al.*, 1972).

Nitrogenase activity was determined by the acetylene reduction technique in filaments incubated for 24 or 48 h in of BG11₀ medium as described (Montesinos *et al.*, 1995). For anaerobic assays, 10 μM DCMU was added to the cell suspension, the flask containing the cells was sealed with a rubber stopper, bubbled with argon for 3 min and further incubated, under culture conditions, for 1 hour before the assay was started by addition of acetylene.

Microscopy and calcein labeling

For standard light microscopy, filaments grown in BG11 medium (in the presence of Sm and Sp for the CSVT3 mutant) were harvested, washed with nitrogen-free medium and resuspended in BG11 or BG11₀ medium with antibiotic for the mutant. After incubation for the indicated times at 30°C in the light on a shaker, samples taken with great care to prevent disruption were visualized by standard light microscopy. About 100 filaments were counted in each case. For staining with Alcian blue, a cell suspension was mixed 1:2 with a 1% Alcian blue (Sigma) solution.

For confocal microscopy of GFP fluorescence, samples from cultures of *Anabaena* sp. set atop solidified medium (BG11 or BG11₀) were visualized using a Leica HCX PLAN-APO

63X 1.4 NA oil immersion objective attached to a Leica TCS SP2 confocal laser-scanning microscope. GFP was excited using 488-nm irradiation from an argon ion laser. Fluorescent emission was monitored by collection across windows of 500-540 nm (GFP imaging) and 630-700 nm (cyanobacterial autofluorescence).

Calcein-staining, FRAP data acquisition and analysis were performed as previously reported (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008). For calcein staining, 0.25 ml of cell cultures were harvested by gentle centrifugation, washed with and resuspended in 0.25 ml fresh growth medium, and then mixed with 5 μ l of calcein-AM (1 mg ml⁻¹ in dimethylsulfoxide). The suspension was incubated in the dark at 30 °C for 90 minutes, and cells were harvested and washed three times in fresh, dye-free growth medium. The suspension was then incubated in the dark for a further 90 minutes before imaging. Cell suspensions were spotted onto agar and placed in a custom-built temperature-controlled sample holder with a glass cover-slip on top, and measurements were carried out at 30 °C.

Cells were imaged with a laser-scanning confocal microscope (Nikon PCM2000) using a 60x oil-immersion objective and the 488 nm line of a 100 mW argon laser (Spectra-Physics) as the excitation source. Chlorophyll fluorescence and dye fluorescence were imaged simultaneously, chlorophyll fluorescence being defined by a Schott RG665 red-glass filter, and dye fluorescence by an interference band-pass filter transmitting between 500 and 527 nm. For imaging, a 20 μ m confocal pinhole was used, giving a point-spread in the Z-direction of about 1.3 μ m (full-width at half-maximum). For FRAP, a 50 μ m pinhole was used, increasing the point-spread in the Z direction to about 2.0 μ m. An initial image was recorded, and the bleach was then carried out by switching the microscope to X-scanning mode, increasing the laser intensity by a factor of 32 by removing neutral density filters, and scanning a line across one cell for 1-2 s. The laser intensity was then reduced again, the microscope was switched back to XY-imaging mode and a sequence of images recorded

typically at 3 s intervals. FRAP data analysis was made using Image Pro Plus 6.2 software (Media Cybernetic Inc.) and modeling by fitting the predicted fluorescence recovery of the bleached cell to the experimental recovery curve by adjusting the time axis to obtain an estimate of E (Mullineaux *et al.*, 2008).

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Figure legends

Figure 1. Northern analysis of the expression of the *fraC* operon (A) and the *fraH* gene region (B). RNA isolated from bubbled cultures of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120, strain CSE2 (*ntcA*) or strain 216 (*hetR*) grown with ammonium (0) and incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen for the times indicated in hours was subjected to hybridization with double-stranded (black bars) or single-stranded (mRNA complementary; open bar) probes of the indicated genes generated by PCR with the indicated primers. Transcript sizes are indicated on the left. Hybridization with an *rnpB* gene probe (Vioque, 1997) was used as a loading and transfer control.

Figure 2. Mutants of the *fra* genes. (A) Schematic of the *fraC* operon and *fraH* genomic regions from *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 with indication of the approximate position and size of DNA fragments removed from *fraC*, *fraD* and *fraH* and the DNA fragment used for insertion of the pCSV3 vector in *fraE*. The approximate positions of the oligonucleotide primers used in PCR analysis of chromosome structure are depicted. (B) PCR analysis of wild type and mutant chromosome structures. DNA from the wild type and each of the mutants was PCR-amplified with the oligonucleotides shown in A. Open triangles point to wild-type DNA; closed triangles point to mutant DNA. In strain CSVT3, mutant DNA carrying an insertion was not observed with the F7/R8 primer pair because of its large size; as a positive control of the presence of amplifiable DNA, amplification with the F8/R8 primer pair is presented. Lambda DNA digested with *Cla*I is shown for reference on the left in each panel. (C) Growth test in solid medium using ammonium, nitrate or N₂ as the nitrogen source. Each spot was inoculated with an amount of cells corresponding to 0.01 µg of Chl, and the plates were incubated under culture conditions for 8 days and photographed.

Figure 3. Filament lengths of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and the *fra* mutants. Filaments grown in BG11 medium (in the presence of 2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ each Sm and Sp for the *fraE* mutant, CSVT3) were harvested, washed with nitrogen-free medium and resuspended in BG11 or BG11₀ medium with antibiotics for the *fraE* mutant. After incubation for the indicated times under culture conditions on a shaker, samples taken with great care to prevent disruption were visualized by standard light microscopy.

Figure 4. Heterocysts in *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and the *fra* mutants. Samples of cultures from 7 days in BG11₀ medium, with antibiotics for the *fraE* mutant, were stained or not with Alcian blue and visualized by light microscopy. Magnification, x1000.

Figure 5. Subcellular localization of SepJ-GFP in the wild-type and *fra* genetic backgrounds. GFP fluorescence micrographs of filaments from bubbled cultures of the indicated strains grown with ammonium or nitrate or grown with ammonium and incubated without combined nitrogen for 8 or 26 h are shown. All samples were taken from bubbled cultures incubated in the presence of antibiotics (Nm and Sm/Sp or CSVT11 and Sm/Sp for the other strains).

Figure 6. Calcein FRAP in *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and the *fra* mutants. Calcein was loaded into filaments of the indicated strains grown with nitrate (in the presence of Sm/Sp for strain CSVT3) as shown by calcein fluorescence in the left images (Pre-bleach). One cell in the filament was subjected to bleaching (line bleach indicated by a white triangle), and the calcein fluorescence in the filament was monitored for several times afterwards (examples at 0, 12, and 27 seconds shown).

Figure 7. Subcellular localization of FraC-GFP and GFP-FraD. Micrographs of filaments from bubbled cultures of the indicated strains grown with nitrate as nitrogen source (NO_3^-) or grown with nitrate and incubated in the absence of combined nitrogen (N_2) for 24 h (CSVT13, CSVT21) or 30 h (CSVT15) are shown. The micrographs are overlays of the red cyanobacterial autofluorescence and the green GFP fluorescence. In the nitrate-grown filaments of strain CSVT13, arrows point to cells that are starting cell division. In the filaments incubated without combined nitrogen, arrows point to heterocysts (which lack or show reduced autofluorescence).

Table 1. Nitrogenase activity of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and *fra* mutants

Strain (genotype)	nmol ethylene produced ($\mu\text{g Chl}$) ⁻¹ h ⁻¹			
	Oxic		Anoxic	
	24 h	48 h	24 h	48 h
PCC 7120 (wild type)	3.2 ± 0.55	6.3 ± 0.67	6.2 ± 0.79	8.2 ± 0.61
CSVT1 (ΔfraC)	0.13 ± 0.07	1.8 ± 0.34	0.84 ± 0.43	3.5 ± 0.5
CSVT2 (ΔfraD)	0.12 ± 0.06	2.4 ± 0.44	0.52 ± 0.26	4.1 ± 0.38
CSVT3 (<i>fraE</i> ::pCSV3)	0	0	0	0.4 ± 0.14
CSVT4 (ΔfraH)	0.03 ± 0.18	0	0	0.15 ± 0.06

Cultures incubated in the absence of combined N for the indicated times were subjected to acetylene reduction assays under oxic or anoxic conditions as described in Experimental procedures. Data are the mean and standard deviation of the mean of 4 (for 24 h) or 6 (for 48 h) independent determinations.

Table 2. Exchange coefficients for calcein transfer between vegetative cells in filaments of *Anabaena* sp. strain PCC 7120 and *fra* mutants

Strain (genotype)	Exchange coefficient, E (s^{-1})	
	BG11	BG11 ₀ (16 h)
PCC 7120 (wild type)	0.049 ± 0.030	0.064 ± 0.061
CSVT1 ($\Delta fraC$)	0.007 ± 0.006	0.005 ± 0.005
CSVT2 ($\Delta fraD$)	0.004 ± 0.006	0.009 ± 0.011
CSVT3 (<i>fraE</i> ::pCSV3)	0.033 ± 0.051	0.022 ± 0.029
CSVT4 ($\Delta fraH$)	0.023 ± 0.017	0.027 ± 0.024

Filaments grown in BG11 medium or incubated in the absence of combined N as indicated (BG11₀) were loaded with calcein, washed and subjected to FRAP analysis as described in Materials and Methods. *t*-Tests indicate that E is significantly different ($P < 0.05$) for all mutants, except for CSVT3 in nitrate, with respect the wild type.